

Photo-Fenton degradation of sunset yellow FCF catalyzed by aromatic additives

Abhilasha Jain, Savitri Lodha, P. B. Punjabi, V. K. Sharma and Suresh C. Ameta*

Photochemistry and Solar Energy Laboratory, Department of Chemistry, University College of Science,
M. L. Sukhadia University, Udaipur-313 002, Rajasthan, India

E-mail : ameta_sc@yahoo.com

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Abstract : Photo-Fenton degradation of dyes will provide a newer method for the treatment of wastewater from dyeing and printing industries. The progress of the reaction has been monitored spectrophotometrically. An effort has been made to observe the effect of various organic additives like hydroquinone, catechol and resorcinol. The effect of variation of various parameters such as pH, concentration of dye, Fe^{3+} ion and additives, amount of H_2O_2 , and light intensity on the rate of photodegradation was also observed. A tentative mechanism for the reaction has been proposed.

Keywords : Sunset yellow, Fenton reagent, photo degradation.

The Fenton reaction has been proved to be an effective method to treat organic pollutants in wastewater¹. The Fenton system consists of Fe^{II} and hydrogen peroxide; the combination of these two has been named as "Fenton reagent". In this system, ferrous ions react with hydrogen peroxide and produces hydroxyl radicals; a powerful oxidizing species. The mechanism and kinetics of the Fenton reaction have been studied by many researchers². But the main drawback is that this reaction stops after complete consumption of ferrous ions. The Fe^{2+} ions can be regenerated from Fe^{3+} ions under the present conditions with additional requirement of light. In presence of light, Fe^{3+} ions react with water molecules and generate $\cdot\text{OH}$ radicals and Fe^{2+} ions. This make this process a cyclic one and photodegradation will proceed more smoothly. This process, which is complemented with UV/visible radiations, is known as photo-Fenton reaction.

A large number of reactions including oxidation of organic compounds, photodegradation of dyes, photo-assisted reactions of various reagents etc. with Fenton's reagent have been carried out by a large number of workers worldwide³.

Although photo-Fenton reaction is a useful tool in the degradation of dyes as well as organic compounds but the major drawback is the slow rate of degradation. It is important and necessary to find out some better and suitable modifications to increase the efficiency and applications of this reagent. In this context, organic additives like hydroquinone, catechol and resorcinol accelerate the rate of reaction.

Results and discussion

An aliquot of 3.0 mL was taken out from the reaction mixture at regular time intervals and the absorbance was measured at $\lambda_{\text{max}} = 480$ nm. It was observed that absorbance of the solution decreases with increasing time of exposure, indicating a decrease in concentration of dye sunset yellow FCF. A plot of $\log [\text{absorbance}]$ versus time was linear and follows pseudo-first order kinetics. The rate constant was measured with the expression :

$$k = 2.303 \times \text{slope}$$

The results are represented in Tables 1a-c.

It was observed that reaction is completed in two stages. The first stage has an induction period; may be for the generation of the $\cdot\text{OH}$ radicals but during this time, a small decrease in absorbance has been observed, which may be attributed as a result of simple photocatalytic degradation of dye. After this slow stage, a major decrease in absorbance has been observed, which seems to be the second stage of photo-Fenton degradation, where $\cdot\text{OH}$ radicals act as oxidizing species for the degradation of the dye. The effect of various parameter on the rate of degradation is studied by comparing the rate of the second stage of the photo-Fenton reaction. In some cases, a slower step has also been observed. Moreover, as the experimental conditions approach the optimum conditions, the time taken by first stage (slow step/induction period) was found to decrease and occasionally becoming zero.

The aromatic additives accelerate the rate of reaction either by reducing the time taken in first stage i.e. $\cdot\text{OH}$ radicals generation becomes faster and/or increasing the rate of second stage.

The observations indicate that the rate of photo-Fenton reaction strongly depends on the pH of the system. In the system, the hydroxyl radicals are generated by steps (vii) and (ix) of mechanism.

Table 1a. A typical run

Hydroquinone system	
[Sunset yellow FCF]	= $1.17 \times 10^{-4} M$
H ₂ O ₂	= 0.1 mL
FeCl ₃	= $2.33 \times 10^{-5} M$
[Hydroquinone]	= $1.67 \times 10^{-5} M$
Intensity	= 60.0 mW cm ⁻²
pH	= 2.50

2 + log O.D.

Time (min)	Treated	Untreated
0.0	2.2981	2.3352
3.0	2.2748	2.3320
6.0	2.2518	2.3273
9.0	2.2156	2.3240
12.0	2.1740	2.3170
15.0	2.1122	2.3062
18.0	2.0326	2.2984
21.0	1.9227	2.2851
24.0	1.7909	2.2699
18.0	1.6454	2.2489
27.0	1.4800	2.2286
30.0	1.2966	2.1931
33.0	1.1238	2.1513
36.0	0.8316	2.0744
39.0	-	2.0281
42.0	-	1.9440
45.0	-	1.8413
48.0	-	1.7168
51.0	-	1.5717
54.0	-	1.4048
57.0	-	1.2479
60.0	-	1.0030
	$k_1 = 3.84 \times 10^{-4} \text{ s}^{-1}$	$k_1 = 1.28 \times 10^{-4} \text{ s}^{-1}$
	$k_2 = 2.56 \times 10^{-3} \text{ s}^{-1}$	$k_2 = 1.92 \times 10^{-4} \text{ s}^{-1}$

Table 1b. A typical run

Catechol system	
[Sunset yellow FCF]	= $8.33 \times 10^{-5} M$
H ₂ O ₂	= 0.1 mL
FeCl ₃	= $2.33 \times 10^{-5} M$
[Catechol]	= $9.33 \times 10^{-5} M$
Light intensity	= 60.0 mW cm ⁻²
pH	= 2.50

1 + log O.D.

Time (min)	Treated	Untreated
0.0	1.3085	1.2487
3.0	1.2437	1.2477
6.0	1.1838	1.2307
9.0	1.1182	1.2219
12.0	1.0557	1.2113
15.0	0.9809	1.2003
18.0	0.9175	1.1806
21.0	0.8450	1.1763
24.0	0.7693	1.1538
27.0	0.6946	1.1322
30.0	0.6170	1.1126
33.0	0.5440	1.0824
36.0	0.4800	1.0374
39.0	0.4082	0.9858
42.0	0.3463	0.9222
45.0	0.2966	0.8530
48.0	0.2479	0.7860
51.0	0.2148	0.7371
54.0	0.1702	0.6748
57.0	0.1398	0.6031
60.0	0.0934	0.5587
63.0	0.0681	0.4785
66.0	0.0453	0.4329
69.0	-	0.3654
72.0	-	0.2833
75.0	-	0.2355
	$k_1 = \text{not observed}$	$k_1 = 2.56 \times 10^{-4} \text{ s}^{-1}$
	$k_2 = 8.96 \times 10^{-4} \text{ s}^{-1}$	$k_2 = 7.68 \times 10^{-4} \text{ s}^{-1}$
	$k_3 = 4.48 \times 10^{-4} \text{ s}^{-1}$	$k_3 = \text{not observed}$

The effect of pH on additive catalyzed photochemical degradation was investigated in the pH range 2.0–3.25. The results are reported in Table 2.

The rate of photo-Fenton degradation of sunset yellow FCF was maximum at pH 2.50, 2.50 and 2.75 for hydroquinone, catechol and resorcinol system, respectively.

Table 1c. A typical run

Resorcinol system		
[Sunset yellow FCF]	= $8.33 \times 10^{-5} M$	
H ₂ O ₂	= 0.1 mL	
FeCl ₃	= $2.33 \times 10^{-5} M$	
[Resorcinol]	= $9.33 \times 10^{-5} M$	
Light intensity	= 60.0 mW cm ⁻²	
pH	= 2.75	
	2 + log O.D.	
Time (min)	Treated	Untreated
0.0	2.1766	2.2019
3.0	2.0762	2.1880
6.0	1.9319	2.1717
9.0	1.6766	2.1423
12.0	1.4683	2.1099
15.0	1.1818	2.0572
18.0	0.9344	1.9894
21.0	0.6220	1.8802
24.0	0.3424	1.7176
27.0	-	1.4941
30.0	-	1.2718
33.0	-	1.0086
36.0	-	0.8573
	$k_1 = 1.54 \times 10^{-3} s^{-1}$	$k_1 = 2.56 \times 10^{-4} s^{-1}$
	$k_2 = 3.84 \times 10^{-3} s^{-1}$	$k_2 = 3.07 \times 10^{-3} s^{-1}$

In steps (iv) and (v) of mechanism, Fe³⁺ ions are reduced to Fe²⁺ ions on reaction with additives. In the mechanism,

steps (vii), (viii) and (xii) also involves the reduction of Fe³⁺ ions to Fe²⁺ ions via reaction with H₂O, H₂O₂ and HO₂· respectively. Fe²⁺ ions further reacts with H₂O₂ and ·OH radicals with the regenerations of Fe³⁺ ions. These ·OH radicals are involved in the photodegradation of the dye through oxidation process. At lower pH value (≤2.0) the steps (vii) and (viii) are comparatively slower in which formation of H⁺ ions is occurred. As the pH of the medium was increased, the rate of reaction also increases because step (vii) and (viii) of mechanism becomes faster. The increase in the rate continues up to pH 2.50, 2.50 and 2.75 for hydroquinone, catechol and resorcinol, respectively. Beyond these specific pH values for each additive, the reaction rate again decreases. This may be attributed to the retardation of step (ix) in which Fe³⁺ ions are regenerated with the simultaneous formation of ·OH ions.

The effect of amount of H₂O₂ on the photocatalytic degradation of sunset yellow FCF was also investigated. The results are reported in Table 3.

The rates were determined in the range from 0.0–0.7 mL. The photo-Fenton degradation of sunset yellow FCF was maximum at 0.1 mL for hydroquinone, catechol and resorcinol systems. Further increase in H₂O₂ amount beyond these limits causes retardation of reaction. This may be explained on the basis that as the amount of H₂O₂ is increased, the rate of reaction increases due to acceleration of step (ix) of mechanism, in which H₂O₂ reacts with Fe²⁺ ion and generates ·OH radicals but a further increase in amount causes the acceleration of step (x) in which H₂O₂ reacts with ·OH radicals and as a consequence, a decrease in the rate of final step (xiii) of mechanism has been observed.

Table 2. Effect of pH on the rate of reaction

pH	Hydroquinone system	Catechol system	Resorcinol system
	$k \times 10^3$ (s ⁻¹)	$k \times 10^4$ (s ⁻¹)	$k \times 10^3$ (s ⁻¹)
	[Sunset yellow FCF] = $1.17 \times 10^{-4} M$	[Sunset yellow FCF] = $8.33 \times 10^{-5} M$	[Sunset yellow FCF] = $8.33 \times 10^{-5} M$
	H ₂ O ₂ = 0.1 mL	H ₂ O ₂ = 0.1 mL	H ₂ O ₂ = 0.1 mL
	FeCl ₃ = $2.33 \times 10^{-5} M$	FeCl ₃ = $2.33 \times 10^{-5} M$	FeCl ₃ = $2.33 \times 10^{-5} M$
	[Hydroquinone] = $1.67 \times 10^{-5} M$	[Catechol] = $9.33 \times 10^{-5} M$	[Resorcinol] = $9.33 \times 10^{-5} M$
	Light intensity = 60.0 mW cm ⁻²	Light intensity = 60.0 mW cm ⁻²	Light intensity = 60.0 mW cm ⁻¹²
2.00	2.48	5.66	2.96
2.25	2.36	7.07	3.05
2.50	2.56	8.96	3.80
2.75	1.95	7.54	3.84
3.00	1.63	6.60	2.78
3.25	1.26	5.66	1.57

Table 3. Effect of amount of H₂O₂ on the rate of reaction

H ₂ O ₂ (mL)	Hydroquinone system	Catechol system	Resorcinol system
	[Sunset yellow FCF] = 1.17 × 10 ⁻⁴ M FeCl ₃ = 2.33 × 10 ⁻⁵ M [Hydroquinone] = 1.67 × 10 ⁻⁵ M Light intensity = 60.0 mW cm ⁻² pH = 2.50	[Sunset yellow FCF] = 8.33 × 10 ⁻⁵ M FeCl ₃ = 2.33 × 10 ⁻⁵ M [Catechol] = 9.33 × 10 ⁻⁵ M Light intensity = 60.0 mW cm ⁻² pH = 2.50	[Sunset yellow FCF] = 8.33 × 10 ⁻⁵ M FeCl ₃ = 2.33 × 10 ⁻⁵ M [Resorcinol] = 9.33 × 10 ⁻⁵ M Light intensity = 60.0 mW cm ⁻² pH = 2.75
	<i>k</i> × 10 ³ (s ⁻¹)	<i>k</i> × 10 ⁴ (s ⁻¹)	<i>k</i> × 10 ³ (s ⁻¹)
0.0	0.27	–	0.30
0.1	2.56	8.96	3.84
0.2	1.62	8.36	2.53
0.3	1.21	5.23	2.15
0.4	1.01	4.78	1.69
0.5	0.94	4.18	0.99
0.6	0.81	3.58	0.54
0.7	0.20	3.28	0.41

Effect of concentration of additives :

The effect of variation of concentration of additives on the photocatalytic degradation of sunset yellow FCF was also investigated. The results are reported in Table 4.

It was observed that rate of reaction increases with the increase in concentration of additives up to 1.67 × 10⁻⁵, 9.33 × 10⁻⁴ and 9.33 × 10⁻⁴ M for hydroquinone, catechol and resorcinol, respectively. On further increase in concentration of additives (hydroquinone and catechol), the rate of reaction decreases. The effect of aromatic additives is so important

that these can significantly accelerate the Fenton reaction of sunset yellow FCF even at very very low concentrations. Moreover, the data show that these additives (hydroquinone and catechol) do not behave only as a catalyst, but also as a reactant, which were attacked by the hydroxyl radicals formed in the reaction process and as a result, the rate of degradation decreases after maxima has been obtained.

The Fenton degradation rates of sunset yellow FCF with different aromatic additives is in the following order :

Hydroquinone > Catechol > Resorcinol.

Table 4. Effect of additive concentration on the rate of reaction

Additive × 10 ⁵ M	Hydroquinone system	Catechol system	Resorcinol system
	[Sunset yellow FCF] = 1.17 × 10 ⁻⁴ M H ₂ O ₂ = 0.1 mL FeCl ₃ = 2.33 × 10 ⁻⁵ M Light intensity = 60.0 mW cm ⁻² pH = 2.50	[Sunset yellow FCF] = 8.33 × 10 ⁻⁵ M H ₂ O ₂ = 0.1 mL FeCl ₃ = 2.33 × 10 ⁻⁵ M Light intensity = 60.0 mW cm ⁻² pH = 2.50	[Sunset yellow FCF] = 8.33 × 10 ⁻⁵ M H ₂ O ₂ = 0.1 mL FeCl ₃ = 2.33 × 10 ⁻⁵ M Light intensity = 60.0 mW cm ⁻² pH = 2.75
	<i>k</i> × 10 ³ (s ⁻¹)	Additive × 10 ⁵ M	<i>k</i> × 10 ⁴ (s ⁻¹)
0.00	–	0.00	5.81
0.33	1.68	2.33	7.74
0.67	1.83	4.67	8.23
1.00	1.97	7.00	8.71
1.33	2.12	9.33	8.96
1.67	2.56	11.67	7.74
2.00	2.19	14.00	7.25
2.33	2.05	–	–

Table 5. Effect of concentration of FeCl₃ on the rate of reaction

Hydroquinone system		Catechol system		Resorcinol system	
[Sunset yellow FCF] = 1.17 × 10 ⁻⁴ M		[Sunset yellow FCF] = 8.33 × 10 ⁻⁵ M		[Sunset yellow FCF] = 8.33 × 10 ⁻⁵ M	
H ₂ O ₂ = 0.1 mL		H ₂ O ₂ = 0.1 mL		H ₂ O ₂ = 0.1 mL	
[Hydroquinone] = 1.67 × 10 ⁻⁵ M		[Catechol] = 9.33 × 10 ⁻⁵ M		[Resorcinol] = 9.33 × 10 ⁻⁵ M	
Light intensity = 60.0 mW cm ⁻²		Light intensity = 60.0 mW cm ⁻²		Light intensity = 60.0 mW cm ⁻²	
pH = 2.50		pH = 2.50		pH = 2.75	
FeCl ₃					
× 10 ⁵	<i>k</i> × 10 ³		<i>k</i> × 10 ⁴		<i>k</i> × 10 ³
<i>M</i>	(s ⁻¹)		(s ⁻¹)		(s ⁻¹)
0.00	-		-		-
0.33	0.41		2.36		0.63
0.67	0.70		4.24		0.86
1.00	1.19		5.66		1.54
1.33	1.31		7.07		2.08
1.67	1.98		7.54		2.62
2.00	2.21		8.48		3.30
2.33	2.56		8.96		3.84

This order is also quite consistent with their ability to be transformed into their corresponding quinone like compounds.

The catalysis by additives could be attributed to their reactions with ferric ions in which ferrous ions are generated with simultaneous transformation of hydroquinone to quinone. It is difficult to oxidise resorcinol directly by ferric ion into a quinone like compound due to its molecular structure. However, hydroxyl radicals can attack resorcinol to generate

hydroxyl substituted hydroquinone, which can promote the Fenton reaction although less efficiently as compared to hydroquinone (step i-iii).

With all the additives, initial induction period was observed when the experimental conditions were away from optimum. By employing aromatic additives, this period becomes shorter and not observed in case of catechol system. At a later stages of reaction, a lag period has also been observed for catechol, where rate of reaction again slows down.

Table 6. Effect of dye concentration on the rate of reaction

Hydroquinone system		Catechol system		Resorcinol system	
H ₂ O ₂ = 0.1 mL		H ₂ O ₂ = 0.1 mL		H ₂ O ₂ = 0.1 mL	
FeCl ₃ = 2.33 × 10 ⁻⁵ M		FeCl ₃ = 2.33 × 10 ⁻⁵ M		FeCl ₃ = 2.33 × 10 ⁻⁵ M	
[Hydroquinone] = 1.67 × 10 ⁻⁵ M		[Catechol] = 9.33 × 10 ⁻⁵ M		[Resorcinol] = 9.33 × 10 ⁻⁵ M	
Light intensity = 60.0 mW cm ⁻²		Light intensity = 60.0 mW cm ⁻²		Light intensity = 60.0 mW cm ⁻²	
pH = 2.50		pH = 2.50		pH = 2.75	
Dye					
× 10 ⁴	<i>k</i> × 10 ³		<i>k</i> × 10 ⁴		<i>k</i> × 10 ³
<i>M</i>	(s ⁻¹)		(s ⁻¹)		(s ⁻¹)
0.67	-		7.68		2.85
0.83	1.99		8.96		3.84
1.00	2.06		6.72		3.70
1.17	2.56		6.40		3.56
1.33	1.95		5.76		3.28
1.50	1.88		5.12		2.99
1.83	1.81		4.80		2.56

Table 7. Effect of light intensity on the rate of reaction

Hydroquinone system [Sunset yellow FCF] = $1.17 \times 10^{-4} M$ $H_2O_2 = 0.1 mL$ $FeCl_3 = 2.33 \times 10^{-5} M$ [Hydroquinone] = $1.67 \times 10^{-5} M$ pH = 2.50		Catechol system [Sunset yellow FCF] = $8.33 \times 10^{-5} M$ $H_2O_2 = 0.1 mL$ $FeCl_3 = 2.33 \times 10^{-5} M$ [Catechol] = $9.33 \times 10^{-5} M$ pH = 2.50	Resorcinol system [Sunset yellow FCF] = $8.33 \times 10^{-5} M$ $H_2O_2 = 0.1 mL$ $FeCl_3 = 2.33 \times 10^{-5} M$ [Resorcinol] = $9.33 \times 10^{-5} M$ pH = 2.75
Light intensity (mW cm ⁻²)	$k \times 10^3$ (s ⁻¹)	$k \times 10^3$ (s ⁻¹)	$k \times 10^3$ (s ⁻¹)
10.0	1.15	4.09	1.84
20.0	1.46	5.89	1.89
30.0	1.52	6.14	2.50
40.0	1.62	7.16	2.84
50.0	1.83	8.70	3.51
60.0	2.56	8.96	3.84
70.0	2.04	8.70	2.67
80.0	2.00	8.19	-

The effect of concentration of ferric ions on the rate of photocatalytic degradation of sunset yellow FCF was observed by keeping all other factors identical. The results are summarised in Table 5. It is clear from the data that the rate of photo-Fenton degradation increases on increasing concentration of ferric chloride. The rates were determined for ferric ion concentration up to concentration $2.33 \times 10^{-5} M$ for all the systems. Because beyond this concentration, the rates were extremely high and it was not possible to record the observations correctly due to experimental limitations. This increasing trend may be explained on the basis that on increasing the concentration of ferric chloride, the concentration of Fe^{2+} ions increases. This results in an enhanced generation of the $\cdot OH$ radicals and as a consequence, the rate of photocatalytic degradation also increases.

The effect of sunset yellow FCF concentration on the rate of its photo-Fenton degradation was observed and the results are summarised in Table 6.

The rate of photo-Fenton degradation was found to increase with increasing concentration of sunset yellow FCF up to $1.17 \times 10^{-4} M$, $8.33 \times 10^{-5} M$ and $8.33 \times 10^{-5} M$ for hydroquinone, catechol and resorcinol system, respectively. Further increase in concentration beyond these limits results in decrease in the rate of degradation. This may be explained on the basis that on increasing the concentration of sunset yellow FCF, the reaction rate increases, since more molecules of dye were available for degradation. But further increase in concentration causes retardation of reaction due to increase in number of collisions between dye molecules themselves whereas probability of collisions between dye and $\cdot OH$ radicals will decrease. As a consequence, retardation in rate of reaction was observed. Unsuitable steric orientation is also one of the factor for a decrease in the rate of reaction.

The effect of light intensity on the photo-Fenton degradation of sunset yellow FCF was investigated. The results are reported in Table 7.

The data indicate that as the light intensity was increased, the rate of reaction also increases and maximum rate of reaction for hydroquinone, catechol and resorcinol systems have been found at $60.0 mW cm^{-2}$.

Further increase in the intensity results in a decrease in the rate of reaction; may be due to thermal reactions.

Mechanism :

On the basis of the experimental observations and corroborating the existing literature, a tentative mechanism has been proposed for the degradation of sunset yellow FCF by photo-Fenton's reagent in presence of aromatic additives.

The aqueous solution of ferric ions on exposure to light generates a proton and $\bullet\text{OH}$ radicals and it is reduced to ferrous state. These ferrous ions further react with H_2O_2 producing hydroxyl ions and hydroxyl radicals and oxidised back to ferric ions. These hydroxyl radicals are the most probable active species in the degradation of dye.

Aromatic compounds can play an important role in catalyzing the Fenton reaction, when these are transformed into hydroquinone like intermediates by the attack of $\bullet\text{OH}$ radicals. In addition, their efficiency to promote the Fenton reaction is closely related to their easiness to be transformed into hydroquinone like intermediates. Hydroquinone like compounds accelerate the Fenton reaction by increasing the regeneration of ferrous ion (e.g. (iv), (v)), which might be the slow step in the mechanism of the simple Fenton reaction. Further, the hydroquinone like compounds are continuously regenerated from quinone or semi-quinone by reacting with HO_2^\bullet radicals and disproportionation reaction; thus, continuously promoting the rate of reaction.

These hydroxyl radicals will degrade the sunset yellow FCF. The participation of $\bullet\text{OH}$ radicals as an active oxidising species was confirmed by using hydroxyl radical scavengers, e.g. isopropanol, where the rate of photodegradation was drastically reduced.

Further, this method has more advantages over other methods. It does not add to pollution any further. The active oxidising species i.e. the hydroxyl radicals will dimerize to give hydrogen peroxide, which may degrade ultimately to water and oxygen. As in this reaction, very low concentration of chemicals is used and the process is cyclic in nature, it is a one of the ecofriendly method for the treatment of waste water.

Conclusion :

The rate of photo-Fenton degradation of sunset yellow FCF is enhanced by aromatic additives. The increasing order of the rate with different additives is as follows :

Hydroquinone > Catechol > Resorcinol

Experimental

All solutions were prepared in doubly distilled water. Irradiation has been carried out with a 200 W tungsten lamp. The light intensity was measured with the help of a solarimeter (CEL, Model SM 201). A water filter has been used to cut off thermal radiations. A digital pH meter (Systronics, Model 335) is used to adjust the pH of the solutions by the addition of previously standardized 0.1 N sulfuric acid and 0.1 N sodium hydroxide solutions. The progress of the photocatalytic reactions was observed by measuring the absorbance at regular time intervals using UV-visible spectrophotometer (Systronics Model 106). Hydroquinone (EM), resorcinol (EM), FeCl_3 (CDH), catechol (CDH) and sunset yellow FCF (Aldrich) have been used as received. Hydrogen peroxide (EM), (concentration 30%, w/v) has been used.

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References

- W. R. Heag and C. C. D. Yao, *Environ. Sci. Technol.*, 1992, **26**, 1005; J. D. Spadaro, L. Zsabelle and V. Ranganathan, *Environ. Sci. Technol.*, 1994, **28**, 1389; W. Spack, R. Bauer and G. Heisler, *Chemosphere*, 1995, **30**, 477; J. Bandeira, C. Morrison, J. Kiwi, C. Plugarin and P. Pevinger, *Photochem. Photobiol. A : Chem.*, 1996, **99**, 57.
- H. J. Fenton, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1894, **65**, 899.

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3. R. Dillert, I. Fomefett, V. Siebus and D. Bahnemann, *J. Photochem. Photobiol.*, 1996, **94A**, 221; J. Polczynska, J. Koealski and A. Sobkowiak, *Polish J. Chem.*, 1998, **72**, 514; R. Augusti, A. O. Diar, L. L. Rocha and R. M. Lago, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1998, **102**, 10723; L. C. Lei, X. J. Hu and P. L. Yue, *J. Photochem. Photobiol.*, 1998, **116A**, 159; H. Gallard, J. Deleat and B. Legude, *New J. Chem.*, 1998, **22**, 263; K. G. Wu, T. Y. Zhang, J. C. Zhao and H. Hidaka, *Chem. Lett.*, 1998, **8**, 857; C. Walling, *Acc. Chem. Res.*, 1998, **31**, 155; F. Chen, W. Ma and J. Zhao, *J. Phys. Chem. (A)*, 2002, **106**, 9485; V. Nadochenko and J. Kiwi, *J. Environ. Sci. Technol.*, 1998, **32**, 3273; D. Sawyer, A. Sobkovich and T. Matsushita, *Acc. Chem. Res.*, 1996, **29**, 1996; G. Ruppert, R. Baur and G. Heisler, *J. Photochem. Photobiol. (A)*, 1993, **73**, 75; J. Kiwi, C. Prilgarin and P. Peringer, *Appl. Cata. (B)*, 1994, **3**, 335.